

Consiglio Nazionale
delle Ricerche

NextGenIT
Consolidation of the Italian Infrastructure
for Omics Data and Bioinformatics

ELIXIR-IT All Hands Meeting 2023

**"Bringing together
Communities and Platforms"**

November 27th-28th

📍 CNR - Rome, Italy

Federated Human Data

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The quest: make “human” data accessible across Europe

The '1+ Million Genomes' (1+MG) initiative aims to enable secure access to genomics and the corresponding clinical data across Europe for better research, personalised healthcare and health policy making.

Since the Digital Day 2018, 25 EU countries (**Italy included**), the UK and Norway signed Member States' [declaration](#).

The bad guys:

Genetic tester 23andMe's hacked data on Jewish users offered for sale online

The stolen data could cover more than half of the company's 14 million customers who have made their information visible to relatives, including distant cousins

By [Joseph Menn](#)

October 6, 2023 at 9:47 p.m. EDT

In this order

Ancestry Service
[REMOVE](#)

Price

USD\$129.00

Update quantity

Ancestry Service

1

Buy now

~~USD\$129~~ USD\$79

Limit 3. Offer ends Nov 27.

- *"Online posts offering the data for sale in underground forums"*
- *"buyers could acquire 100 profiles for \$1,000 or as many as 100,000 for \$100,000"*
- *"a large database of Ashkenazi Jews ... include people with even 1% Jewish ancestry."*

The worst case scenario I ([more here](#))

“China wants to make the country’s Uighurs, a predominantly Muslim ethnic group, more subservient to the Communist Party Collecting genetic material is a key part of China’s campaign, according to human rights groups and Uighur activists ... they also relied on genetic material from people around the world that was provided by Kenneth Kidd, a prominent Yale University geneticist.”

The worst case scenario II ([more here](#))

Science

<https://www.science.org> > content > article > invented-pe... ⋮

The 'invented persona' behind a key pandemic database

Apr 19, 2023 — Illustration of two scientists pulling aside a coronavirus-patterned curtain to reveal a man standing. Control issues. GISAID offers a safe ...

The rules: (the tragic part)

General Data Protection Regulation GDPR

Welcome to gdpr-info.eu. Here you can find the official [PDF](#) of the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation) in the current version of the OJ L 119, 04.05.2016; cor. OJ L 127, 23.5.2018 as a neatly arranged website. All Articles of the GDPR are linked with suitable recitals. The European Data Protection Regulation is

- genomic data is (highly) sensitive
 - warrant highest level of protection
- whatever highest level of protection actually means is unclear,
 - even to (especially) regulatory bodies
- yet, we do not fully understand all the implications!

The strategy (ELIXIR-inspired)

What personal data is considered sensitive?

- personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs;
- trade-union membership;
- **genetic data**, biometric data processed solely to identify a human being;
- **health-related data**;
- data concerning a person's sex life or sexual orientation.

Article 4(13), (14) and (15) and Article and Recitals (51) to (56) of the GDPR

European
Genomic Data
Infrastructure

2018

2020

2022

2023

2026

2027

The plan:(Elixir-led)

1. [B1MG \(2020-2023\)](#): design the infrastructure for storing and sharing the data
2. [GDI \(2023-2026\)](#): deploy the infrastructure across Europe
3. [GoE \(2024-2027\)](#): populate with data

Testing and development of tools and technologies:

Implementation studies:

- Beacon
- Federated ECA

The goal: an ecosystem of service providers working together with data creators, access governance and users

Voisin et al., 2021, Cell Genomics 1, 100030
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xgen.2021.100030>

The tools: (almost there)

INFRASTRUCTURE

Secure cross-border data access roadmap (Deliverable)	Available
Secure data access demonstrator (PoC) (Video / Slides)	(May-22)
Secure cross-border data access roadmap updated	Ongoing (May-23)

Data
discovery

Access
management tools

Data
processing

Data
reception

Storage and
interfaces

Beacon

Beacon

- Data discovery tool supporting tiered access for controlled access genetic datasets
- Can be networked

Beacon v2

- Adds variant types and filters
- Different responses can be at different access levels
 - Helps minimize re-identification issues
 - Different legal requirements

Have you seen deletions in this region on chromosome 9 in Glioblastomas from a juvenile patient, in a dataset with unrestricted access?

Beacon v2 API

The Beacon API v2 proposal opens the way for the design of a simple but powerful "genomics API".

Federated EGA

- Harmonised platform for archival, discovery, access, and distribution of controlled access human data
- **Federated model** – Data remains within country or institution
 - Scalable
 - ELSI Issues
- Supports federated network of repositories, data hubs, and local or remote cloud analysis environments
- EGA GDPR: -> PoC real data (see [here](#))

Resource Entitlement Management System (REMS)

- Tool for managing access rights to resources, such as research datasets or Biobanks
- Utilises the ELIXIR Authorisation and Authentication Infrastructure
- Maintains a list of permissions for a particular individual within a REMS instance
- May be centralised, federated, or hybrid model
- Already in use for existing resources
 - E.g <https://thl-biobank.elixir-finland.org/>
 - Euro Bioimaging

Success story (in the making):

B1MG *implemented a Proof of Concept (PoC)* of a federated infrastructure for sharing genomic data

- Mirror PoC in Italy
- **4+1 institutions (4 clinical institutions)**
- share (synthetic data) across institutions
- **scale up to real data**

Aims: Italy's PoC

- promote the development/maintenance of required services by ELIXIR-IT.
- coordinated effort with MoH (MinSal): aim fill in some gaps

main functionalities

TOOLS:

 = not available in our country

 = used or tested in this PoC

 = Provided as a service by ELIXIR-IT

Sister project: CCM MinSal (PoC)

- 1) Institutions OPBG, Gaslini, San Raffaele, IRST-Meldola
- 2) Synthetic data from EGA
- 3) Protocol for sequencing and deposit real data at EGA (UCSC+Sant'Anna)

- 1) Beacon as a service (ELIXIR)

1) *Federated EGA (ELIXIR)? Can we use the central EGA?*

- 1) AAI/REMS

State of the art (as of ELIXIRxNextGenIT)

Tool

Status-current

Status pre

Deployed

Deployment started

More later...

More later...

The team (our heroes)

**Consiglio Nazionale
delle Ricerche**

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Federico Zambelli

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Claudio Lo

Giudice

Roberto Cilli

How to engage

Giacinto Donvito

- Just make contact with the community
- Implementing all this stuff is going to be a long and complex journey.
- Any help is welcome

Nadina Foggetti

Erika Ferrandi

